

First observation of sand-covering by the Lesser Octopus *Eledone cirrhosa*

Primera observación sobre el enterramiento del pulpo blanco *Eledone cirrhosa*

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Recibido el 28-X-2005. Aceptado el 16-II-2006

ABSTRACT

The behavioural pattern of sand-covering is observed and described for the first time in the lesser octopus *Eledone cirrhosa*. The specimen developed a burrowing/burying behaviour which lasted approximately 50 seconds. The burrowing/burying continued until the animal was totally covered except for its eyes. This behavioural pattern is similar to the first phase of sand covering found in *Sepia* spp and various species of sepiolids. Information available did not allow to conclude whether this sand-covering behavioural pattern should be defined as burying or, on the contrary, as burrowing.

RESUMEN

Se describe, por vez primera, el enterramiento del pulpo blanco *Eledone cirrhosa*. El tiempo empleado por el ejemplar para desarrollar esa pauta de comportamiento fue de unos 50 segundos. El enterramiento continuó hasta que el animal estuvo totalmente cubierto por la arena, excepto los ojos. Esta pauta es semejante a la primera fase de enterramiento observada en *Sepia* spp y varias especies de sepiólidos.

KEY WORDS: *Eledone cirrhosa*, sand-covering, burrowing/burying behaviour, cephalopods.

PALABRAS CLAVE: *Eledone cirrhosa*, enterramiento, comportamiento, cefalópodos.

INTRODUCTION

Cephalopods have many ways of minimizing the risk of detection by predators. Two of them are burying and burrowing (HANLON AND MESSENGER, 1996). *Burying* is defined by HANLON AND MESSENGER (1996) as "the act of covering oneself with the substrate (or diving into it), resulting in temporary concealment". Sepioids and Sepiolids bury themselves partially or completely

to conceal themselves and avoid their predation or maximise the efficiency to capture preys (BOLETZKY AND BOLETZKY, 1970; BOLETZKY, 1977; SINGLEY, 1983; MATHER, 1986; HANLON, 1988). Some benthic octopuses like *Octopus burryi* and *Eledone moschata* bury quickly into the substrate (mud or sand) for immediate predator avoidance (HANLON AND HIXON, 1980; MANGOLD, 1983).

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The behavioural pattern of this sand-covering is well established at hatching (BOLETZKY, 1977) and is comparatively simple in *Sepia* (MATHER, 1986; HANLON AND MESSENGER, 1988). When the animal settles on the bottom, it blows away the sand from underneath its body by jetting water through the funnel. The sand particles thus whirl up and descend upon the cuttlefish, which gradually settles deeper until it is entirely covered. In sepiolids, there are, however, two phases (BOLETZKY AND BOLETZKY, 1970; BOLETZKY, 1983). The first corresponds to what is known in *Sepia* and consists of a series of flushing movements by which the animals blow up sand from underneath their body with vigorous funnel jets. Fin movements counteract the propulsive effect of these jets. With increasing age, this process is generally achieved more quickly than at younger stages, and the animals are almost totally covered except for the dorsal surface of the head. A second phase follows in which the animal stretches out its dorso-lateral arms and gathers sand around to cover the head and neck areas, with a series of sweeping movements. In contrast to the first phase, the second tends to become longer with age. Apparently there is no visual or tactile feedback indicating to the animal when the sand cover is complete, and afterwards, the animals remain virtually motionless. The funnel pouch only maintains the respiratory cycle, expanding and contracting slowly, the end of the funnel tube protruding laterally at the surface of the sand between head and mantle. There is an actual state of total quiescence where animals do not react to feeble stimuli (HANLON AND MESSENGER, 1996). All these observations clearly show that the Sepiolineae are fully adapted to bottom life (as the Rossiinae). At the same time, however, they are also well adapted to life in open water; being good swimmers able to pursue and capture fast-moving prey in the water column far from the bottom (BOLETZKY, 1983).

In *Euprymna scolopes*, after an initial active phase where the post-hatching juveniles swim almost constantly and seldom burrow, the animals hatched in the laboratory begin to borrow in the

sand for progressively longer periods and after 5 to 6 days spend most daylight hours buried in the substratum (SINGLEY, 1983). In the comparative study of the sand covering behaviour in different species of *Sepioloa* and *Sepietta* (BOLETZKY AND BOLETZKY, 1970), specific differences in reaction time were observed. The shortest reaction times were observed in *Sepietta obscura* and *Sepioloa robusta*. As all tested animals were laboratory reared, hence fully acclimated to the artificial test situation, these specific differences appear meaningful in terms of the behavioural characteristic of the species. However, the behaviour pattern of sand-covering does not show any distinct differences among species.

Sand covering behaviour is different to *burrowing*, which is defined by HANLON AND MESSENGER (1996) as "the construction of semi-permanent dens or refuges where none exist previously; protracted excavation and residence longer than a few minutes are implied in this definition". Burrowing is performed only by octopuses and occurs in a variety of habitats. *Octopus dofleini* burrows in sand or sand and mud mixture (HARTWICK, THORANISSON AND TULLOCH, 1978), *O. macropus* makes narrow deep holes in sand (HOCHBERG AND COUCH, 1971; HANLON, 1988), *O. cyanea* burrows dens in coral rubble (YARNALL, 1969; FORSYTHE AND HANLON, 1997), *O. bimaculoides* burrows in soft mud by constructing elaborate stone-lined holes, and *O. vulgaris* builds dens by collecting stones and empty shells to block the entrance of a depression (WOODS, 1965). The time taken to construct a burrow varies greatly. Thus, YARNALL (1969) reported 5 minutes and FORSYTHE AND HANLON (1997) 20 minutes for *O. cyanea* digging in coral rubble. AMBROSE (1982) reported "a matter of minutes" for small *O. bimaculatus* (c. 75 g) but Hanlon (per. commun. 1988) observed 25 minutes.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A scuba-diver (JLG) obtained information and pictures of an unsexed live

Figure 1. Sequence of the burrowing behaviour observed for the first time in a specimen of *Eledone cirrhosa*. See text for explanation.

Figura 1. Secuencia del enterramiento observado por vez primera en un ejemplar de Eledone cirrhosa. Véase el texto para explicación.

90 mm mantle length and 120 g body weight *Eledone cirrhosa* (Lamarck, 1798). This specimen was captured by a trawler on the Galician shelf (NW Spain) on 18 March 2005 at a depth of 150 m. The animal was taken onshore a

few hours later without any trace of apparent lesion and maintained alive in a 50 l tank equipped with an open-system of water circulation. Three days later, it was deposited in a sandy/muddy bottom at 12 m depth in

the Ría de Vigo (NW Spain) where it was photographed *in situ*.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the Ría, the animal displayed a sand covering behaviour which lasted 50 seconds approximately. Afterwards, the animal moved a few meters and burrowed again very quickly and later expelled ink and swam away from the diver. The sequence of the burrowing behaviour is shown in Figure 1.

The animal was placed on the bottom after being released and seemingly familiarised itself with the substratum (Fig. 1A). It started to burrow in the sand immediately and the diver was able to record a clear pattern. At first, small grains of sand and mud were thrown up simultaneously from underneath the arms, forward and backwards. However, the circle surrounding the posterior part of the mantle, formed by the expulsion of sand backwards, did not cover the whole animal. The mantle and the head stayed totally motionless and the arms were placed close together, almost perpendicular to the body axis and twisting in their proximal and distal parts, respectively. The animal stayed that way and repeated these actions for ten-twelve seconds (Figs. 1B-D). A few seconds later, the animal made a hole under the anterior part of the mantle and then sunk in the sand with the man-

tle upwards (Fig. 1E). The arms formed a circle and the specimen started throwing out sand and mud from underneath all its body. Afterwards, the posterior part of the mantle and the head settled deeper into the sand, while keeping the arms extended and the eyes, neck and dorsal part of the mantle uncovered (Fig. 1F). The burrowing continued (Fig. 1G) until the animal was totally covered except for the eyes (Fig. 1H)

The behavioural pattern of this sand-covering is similar to the first phase found in *Sepia* and various species of sepiolids. When the animal settles on the bottom it makes a series of flushing movements by which the animals blow up sand from underneath their body with vigorous funnel jets. The sand particles thus whirl up and descend upon the cuttlefish, which gradually settles deeper until it is entirely covered. However, in our observation there was no second phase as observed in sepiolids.

The information we obtained did not allow us to infer whether this behavioural pattern should be defined as burying or, on the contrary, as a burrowing (HANLON AND MESSENGER, 1996). Differences between both patterns are so subtle that several authors (BOLETZKY, 1983; MANGOLD, 1983) use both terms indifferently. In any case, the observed behaviour, which is described for the first time in the lesser octopus *Eledone cirrhosa*, can be called sand covering.

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